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Finding Solace amidst Pandemic

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Abstract: In a time of global pandemics, people are understandably frightened, and try to associate with the “End Time” sayings in the Synoptic Gospels and in the book of Revelation. It is true that in the Synoptics Jesus warns His disciples that “pestilences” will be one of the signs of the “last days” of human history, a time of shaking the world to wake up and realize that Jesus’ return to judge and reign over the earth is increasingly imminent. However, we must be also realistic that in the history, pandemics have come and gone many times. So rather than reflexively sharing or getting panic about how these are certainly signs that Jesus will be back to create a new heaven and a new earth, stop and consider if that is really true. Remember, the “End Time” sayings in the Synoptic Gospels and in the book of Revelation should be understood within the parameters of the apocalyptic literature. The author shows that no matter how severe a trial is, we should never assume God is not listening or does not care.

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In a time of global pandemics, people are understandably frightened, and try to associate with the “End Time” sayings in the Synoptic Gospels (cf. Mt 24; Mk 13; Lk 21) and in the book of Revelation (cf. Rev 9:18.20; 11:6; 13:3.12.14; 15:1.6.8;

16:9.21:18:4.8; 21:9; 22:18). It is true that in the Synoptics Jesus warns His disciples that “pestilences” will be one of the signs of the “last days” of human history, a time of shaking the world to wake up and realize that Jesus’ return to judge and reign over the earth is increasingly imminent (cf. Mt 24:3-8; Lk 21:10-12). However, we must be also realistic that in the history, pandemics have come and gone many times. So rather than reflexively sharing or getting panic about how these are certainly signs that Jesus will be back to create a new heaven and a new earth (cf. Isa 65:17, Rev 21:1), stop and consider if that is really true. Remember, the “End Time” sayings in the Synoptic Gospels and in the book of Revelation should be understood within the parameters of the apocalyptic literature.

We may read these passages through our specific eschatological ideas, but we should be reasonable and careful in sharing and imposing our views to others. Many people share, especially in the social media, their own personal views with specific agendas, hoping to incite some level of fear or panic about the future. However, we should not fall prey to these tactics, but prayerfully consider if what is being said truly aligns with what God has revealed to us in Scripture. Many false prophets throughout history have sought their own benefit in leading people astray (cf. 2 Pet 2:1). God knows when he will bring about the consummation and Christ will return, and we can trust him with doing what is righteous. Rather than guessing its future specificities, we should simply be reminded that we look forward to a day when God will walk again among his people. Rather than despairing over the brokenness we see in the world, it should impel us to tell others of the hope we have in the coming of Christ and the restoration of the earthly community with the heavenly community.

What Jesus says in Luke 21 is very consoling:

Teacher, they exclaimed! “When? And will there be any warning ahead of time?” He (Jesus) replied, “Don’t let anyone mislead you. For many will come announcing themselves as the Messiah, and saying, ‘The time has come.’ But don’t believe them! And when you hear of wars and insurrections beginning, don’t panic. True, wars must come, but the end won’t follow immediately-for nation shall rise against nation and kingdom against kingdom, and there will be great earthquakes, and famines in many lands, and epidemics, and terrifying things happening in the heavens. This will give you an opportunity to testify” (Lk 21:7-13).

Jesus makes four things clear here: do not be deceived or surprised, do not panic, be patient and witness: “This will be your opportunity to bear witness” (Lk 21:13). So, occasions like this is an opportunity for us to practice and witness Christian charity and love. Jesus also told us how to respond in such dark times. “Now when these things begin to happen, *look up and lift up your heads*, because your redemption draws near” (Lk 21:28).

Does the Bible give Directions to find Solace amidst Pandemic?

The Bible also gives us certain directions to cope with the pandemic situations. Just to mention a few:

1. **Prayer:** Prayer would be a right step to begin with, as it assures us God’s help. The Scripture invites us to pray individually as well as together for oneself and for others. “Don’t worry about anything; instead, pray about everything; tell God your needs, and don’t forget to thank him for his answers” (Phil 4:6). See the following Old Testament passages for the exemplary models of praying for oneself and for others: Gen 18:22-23; Num 14:13-23; 1Sam 2:1-10; 12:20-25; 2 Sam 7:18-29; 1 Kgs 3:5-15; 2 Kgs 19:15-19; 2 Chr 7:14; Jon 2:2-9; Jer 29:12; 32:16-25; Ezra 9:6-15; Neh 1:4-11; Dan 9:3-19; Job 42:1-6.10. See also 1 Tim 2:1-3;

- Eph 6:18; Jn 14:13;15:7; Lk 18:1; 1 Thess 5:17; Rom 12:12; Mt 5:44; 6:6; Mk 11:24; 1 Pet 3:12; Col 1:9-12; 4:2; 1 Jn 5:14 etc.
2. **Ask for wisdom patiently:** Solomon's prayer for wisdom (1 Kgs 3:7-13) would be an inspiring instance as how to seek God's help to understand various pandemic situation scientifically and theologically. James 1:2-6 may also guide us in our search of understanding various pandemic situations as it assures us that God can give us wisdom to follow this time: "If you want to know what God wants you to do, ask him, and he will gladly tell you, for he is always ready to give a bountiful supply of wisdom to all who ask him; he will not resent it" (Jas 1:4-6).
 3. **Trust in God's care:** Trust in the providential care of the Lord who took care of his people in the wilderness for 40 years. Psalm 91:2-14 may give a foundational experience for this trust: "God alone is my refuge, my place of safety; he is my God, and I trust him. For he rescues you from every trap and protects you from the fatal plague. He will shield you with his wings! They will shelter you. His faithful promises are your armor. Now you don't need to be afraid of the dark anymore, nor fear the dangers of the day; nor dread the plagues of darkness, nor disasters in the morning" (Ps 91:2-6). See the following passages where God's providential care is unraveled: Isa 49:15; Pss 23:1; 103:13-14; 115:12; 121:3; Mt 6:32; 10:30-31; Lk 12:7.30: 15:20; Jn 10:13-14 etc.
 4. **Be hopeful:** it is natural to get disappointed with this sort of hopeless situation but the Scripture teaches us to be hopeful and courageous, because it assures us that: God has solutions to our problems (1 Cor 10:13); God's grace is sufficient for our every need (2 Cor 9:8); God is able to do more that we ask or imagine (Eph 3:20); God is always faithful (Lam 3:32); Hope is the anchor for our grieved soul (Heb 6:19-20); put your hope in God (Ps 42:5); put your hope in a faithful and almighty god (Ps 146: 3-10); hope produces endurances and perseverance (1 Thess 1:3)

etc.. See also Deut 31:6; Ps 39:7; 42:11; 43:5; 71:5; 119:14.81; 130:5; 146:5; Job 5;15-16; Mk 9:23; 1 Tim 6:17; Heb 11:1; Rom 15:13 etc.

5. **Be a witness:** Jesus says very clearly that “this will be your opportunity to bear witness” (Lk 21:13). James 2:24 says that “a person is justified by works and not by faith alone.” COVID-19 is creating new needs, while putting enormous financial pressure on all sectors of life. This is the time to reach out to local charities and ask how we can best support them with our time and resources. In addition to taking all the steps to follow crucial safety guidelines for ourselves and our communities, we need to ask constantly: what can we do to help the individuals and communities affected by the COVID-19 pandemic? See Deut 15:10; Isa 58:10; Mt 25:35; Lk 6:38; 11:41; 12:33.48; Acts 20:35; Rom 12:7-8.10-13; 1 Cor 13:3; 2 Cor 9:6-8; Phil 2:3-4; 1 Jn 3:17 etc.
6. **Draw inspiration from the afflicted:** Draw inspiration from the biblical characters who faced the situation of the pestilences and diseases. Just to mention only two: King David in 2 Sam 24 and Job in the book of Job.
 - **King David:** In 2 Sam 24, King David in his arrogance ordered to muster the people and consequently he was warned by the prophet Gad that he would be punished. Through the prophet Yahweh makes David to choose and he is asked to choose between famine, military defeat, or plague (24:13). However, David concludes that the judgment of mortals is unpredictable, whereas God’s judgment is consistently moderated by his mercy and, therefore, he says, “let us fall into the hands of the Lord, for his mercy is great” (24:14). The first evil, famine, is caused by God, and one can survive it only by depending on the mercy of other people (cf. Gen 45). The second, “the sword,” comes from the enemy. To flee from the enemy in battle is considered disgraceful (cf. 2 Sam 19:4).

So, David does not even think of this option. The third evil, pestilence, comes directly from God, and survival depends totally on the mercy of God. Thus, David resolves to “fall into the hand of the Lord” (24:14). In ordering the census, David is acting like a king of any other nation. In his response, however, he is not an arrogant king but a man of faith. The king who had said, “Go ... number the people” (24:2) has forsaken that mode of royal pretention and now speaks as a servant of the covenant (24:14). David knows that in wrath Yahweh will show his mercy (cf. Hab 3:2), and his judgment on his people is moderated by compassion (Isa 28:21). He knows from experience (cf. 2 Sam12:13) that the Lord would be more merciful than any of his enemies, and the king prefers the wounds of a friend (cf. Ps 141:5; Prov 27:6) - especially a divine one - to those of an enemy. Therefore now he places himself in God’s hands (24:14) rather than suffer those other punishments in which the will of man seems to have a greater share (24:11-13). He prefers to fall into the hands of God, whose heart is ready for pardon.

- **Job:** The account of Job in Scripture may help righteous people, when they go through discouraging and traumatic experiences, to learn to trust God patiently while awaiting the resolution of their problems. Job was an exceptionally righteous man. He carefully avoided acts of transgression against God’s laws. He behaved blamelessly (Job 1:1). God decided to test Job’s character to see how his commitment to Him would bear up under adversity (cf. Job 1:8.12-19). Even in the midst of the loss of family and excruciating boils (Job 1:12-19), he could say, “The Lord gave, and the Lord has taken away; blessed be the name of the Lord” (Job 1:21). Job withstood all the faulty reasoning and accusations of his three friends (cf. Job 4-31). However, during his ordeal of loss and

suffering, Job gradually came to resent God, and his principal objection was that God was unresponsive to him, that He was not properly acknowledging his righteousness. God challenged Job, suggesting that he try to tame a sea creature, a great beast that was “made without fear” (cf. Job 41:1-10.33-34). In the end Job saw that the basis of his problem was his lack of understanding and excessive confidence in his own righteousness. Then his view of God’s fairness changed. He saw that His critical attitude toward God was wrong: “I have uttered what I did not understand, things too wonderful for me, which I did not know . . . I have heard of You by the hearing of the ear, but now my eye sees You. Therefore I abhor myself, and repent in dust and ashes” (Job 42:3-6). Job’s experiences can explain why righteous people may go through discouraging and traumatic times and be tempted to resent God for not obviously and quickly intervening on their behalf.

Conclusion

Repeatedly in the Bible, we see that God in His mercy shakes individuals and nations in a desire to get their attention and draw them to Him (cf. Am 9:9; Hag 2:7; Heb 12:26). However, the Lord in His loving kindness promised to be gracious to forgive and heal the people of Israel if they were stricken with terrible diseases and then repented of their sins. For example:

- In 2 Chronicles 7:12-14 we read: “Then the Lord appeared to Solomon at night and said to him, ‘I have heard your prayer and have chosen this place for Myself as a house of sacrifice. If I shut up the heavens so that there is no rain, or if I command the locust to devour the land, or if I send pestilence among My people, and My people who are called by My name humble themselves and pray and seek My face and turn from their wicked ways, then I will hear from

- heaven, will forgive their sin and heal their land.”
- In Jeremiah 18:7-8 the Lord says: “At one moment I might speak concerning a nation or concerning a kingdom to uproot, to pull down, or to destroy it. If that nation against which I have spoken turns from its evil, I will relent concerning the calamity I planned to bring on it.”

No matter how severe a trial is, we should never assume God is not listening or does not care. He sees lessons we need to learn that are beyond our present understanding. Dr. Darrell Bock, theologian and professor at Dallas Theological Seminary notes that “Plagues are a way that God seeks to get our attention about our finitude and mortality as well as how we are giving attention to God. They are an opportunity for reflection about how we live and a reminder we are not gods ourselves” (Cited in Renshaw 2020). Yes, the Bible teaches that God uses pestilence to judge Israel and the nations both individually and collectively. He uses them to warn the people and nations to get their attention and draw them to a right and healthy and joyful relationship with Him. What the Bible teaches in such times is that we individually and collectively seek God’s forgiveness and fall into his hands imploring his mercy.

References

- Pandikattu, Kuruvilla (ed). 2020. *Have Courage, I am with You: Christian Responses to Covid-19*. New Delhi: Media House.
- Renshaw, Jessica. 2020. “What Does the Bible Teach About Pestilence, Plagues and Global Pandemics? By Joel Rosenberg.” *Hiddeninjesus* (blog). March 29, 2020. <https://hiddeninjesus.wordpress.com/2020/03/29/what-does-the-bible-teach-about-pestilence-plagues-and-global-pandemics-by-joel-rosenberg/>.

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